

NURSING STUDENTS' AWARENESS LEVEL OF CONFLICT AND VIOLENCE AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS BRAIN DRAIN: A DESCRIPTIVE AND RELATIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between nursing students' awareness level towards conflict and violence and their attitudes towards brain drain. This descriptive and correlational study included 260 students who were continuing their active education in the nursing department of a state university and agreed to participate in the study. The data of the study were collected using the "Introductory Information Form", "Conflict and Violence Awareness Scale (CVAS)" and "Nursing Students' Attitude Scale Towards Brain Drain (ASBD)" between March 15 and April 15, 2023. It was found that 34.6% of the students wanted to work abroad after graduation, and 74.2% stated the reason for this as "to live a better quality life". The students' total ASBD score averages were 54.27 ± 13.94 and the total CVAS score averages were 94.03 ± 25.32 . The total ASBD mean scores of male students who want to work abroad after graduation and who evaluate the health services in Turkey and the society's perspective on the nursing profession as "very bad" were found to be significantly higher than the other groups ($p < 0.05$). A negative significant relationship was found between the CVAS and ASBD of nursing students ($r = -0.294$; $p < 0.05$), and a positive significant relationship was found between ASBD and age ($r = 0.193$; $p < 0.05$). It was determined that the students' awareness levels regarding conflict and violence and their attitudes towards brain drain were above average. It was determined that as the awareness levels of nursing students regarding conflict and violence increased, their tendency to migrate decreased.

Keywords: Brain Drain, Conflict, Nursing, Student, Violence.

HEMŞİRELİK ÖĞRENCİLERİNİN ÇATIŞMA VE ŞİDDET KONUSUNDAKİ FARKINDALIK DÜZEYİ VE BEYİN GÖÇÜNE İLİŞKİN TUTUMLARI: TANIMLAYICI VE İLİŞKİSEL BİR ARAŞTIRMA

Öz

Bu çalışma, hemşirelik öğrencilerinin çatışma ve şiddete yönelik farkındalık düzeyi ile beyin göçüne yönelik tutumu arasındaki ilişkiyi belirlemek amacıyla yapıldı. Tanımlayıcı ve ilişki arayıcı tipte yapılan bu araştırmaya bir devlet üniversitesinin hemşirelik bölümünde aktif öğrenimine devam etmekte olan ve çalışmaya katılmayı kabul eden 260 öğrenci dahil edildi. Araştırmanın verileri "Tanıtıcı Bilgiler Formu", "Çatışma ve Şiddete İlişkin Farkındalık Ölçeği (ÇŞFÖ)" ve "Hemşirelik Öğrencilerinde Beyin Göçüne Yönelik Tutum Ölçeği (BGYTÖ)" kullanılarak, 15 Mart-15 Nisan 2023 tarihleri arasında toplandı. Öğrencilerin %34.6'sının mezun olduktan sonra yurt dışında çalışmak istediği, bunun nedenini %74.2'si "daha kaliteli hayat yaşamak" olarak belirttiği saptandı. Öğrencilerin BGYTÖ toplam puan ortalamaları 54.27 ± 13.94 ve ÇŞFÖ toplam puan ortalamaları 94.03 ± 25.32 'dir. Erkek cinsiyetin, mezuniyet sonrası yurt dışında çalışmak isteyen ve Türkiye'deki sağlık hizmetlerini ve toplumun hemşirelik mesleğine bakış açısını "çok kötü" olarak değerlendiren öğrencilerin BGYTÖ toplam puan ortalamaları diğer gruplara göre anlamlı derecede yüksek bulundu ($p < 0.05$). Hemşirelik öğrencilerinin ÇŞFÖ ile BGYTÖ arasında negatif yönde anlamlı ilişki ($r = -0.294$; $p < 0.05$), BGYTÖ ile yaş arasında pozitif yönde anlamlı ilişki saptandı ($r = 0.193$; $p < 0.05$). Öğrencilerin çatışma ve şiddete ilişkin farkındalık düzeylerinin ve beyin göçüne yönelik tutumlarının ortalamasının üzerinde olduğu belirlendi. Hemşirelik öğrencilerinin çatışma ve şiddete yönelik farkındalık düzeyleri arttıkça göç etme eğilimlerinin azaldığı belirlendi.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Beyin Göçü, Çatışma, Hemşirelik, Öğrenci, Şiddet.

1. INTRODUCTION

Healthcare institutions have become settings where negative conflict processes and violence are experienced by both patients and healthcare professionals, influenced by the socio-psychological context (1). Workplace violence in the health sector has detrimental effects on the physical and mental well-being of individuals (2,3). Among healthcare professionals, nursing students are particularly vulnerable to violence due to various reasons, like their young age, limited clinical experience, frequent rotations in clinical practice, and challenges in effective communication with patients and colleagues (4,5). Such incidents of violence have adverse consequences for nursing students' educational journeys, their perceptions of the nursing profession, and their professional attitudes and roles (6,7). Nursing students exposed to violence experience increased anxiety levels and absenteeism in clinical practice (8). All these negative effects can push students towards graduation to worry about the future and seek better living conditions.

Throughout history, relocation has occurred with varying characteristics, often driven by the desire to access resources and improve living conditions. In recent times, brain drain has emerged as a significant migration phenomenon, witnessing a notable increase in migration rates and posing as a sociological problem (9,10).

Among various professional groups, healthcare workers experience one of the highest rates of brain drain (11). The migration of health workers has been increasing since the mid-1970s. (12-14). For example, while only 5% of nurses worked away from their hometowns in the 1970s, today this rate is stated to be 60% (15-16). Many factors such as the disappearance of borders between countries, globalization, increased transportation and communication opportunities, advancement of technology and policies encouraging migration in developed countries have been effective in the increase of migration (15). It is predicted that in the future, the growing disparity between the supply and demand of healthcare workers will further contribute to increased migration and that the majority of those who migrate abroad are highly educated and skilled individuals (16,17).

Globally, there is a recognized need for qualified nursing professionals, and this demand is expected to persist in the coming years (18). Demands from foreign countries, combined with negative factors fed from within, can be effective in increasing brain drain. For this reason, there is a need for research that will evaluate the brain drain and reverse brain drain tendencies of nursing students and the factors that may be effective in planning health manpower and organizing migration movements without causing loss of manpower. It is thought that violence and conflicts in the health sector may be a negative factor that feeds the brain drain trend from within. After all these considerations, the present study aims to explore the relationship between nursing students' awareness of conflict and violence and their attitude toward brain drain.

Research Questions

- What is the level of awareness of nursing students toward conflict and violence?
- What is the attitude of nursing students toward brain drain?
- Is there a relationship between the level of awareness of nursing students toward conflict and violence and their attitude toward brain drain?

2. METHODS

2.1. Type of the research

This study adopts a descriptive and correlational research design.

2.2. Location and time

The study was conducted among nursing students currently enrolled in a state university in Turkey between March 15 and April 15, 2023.

2.3. Population and sample of the research

The population of the study comprised 387 undergraduate nursing students studying at the faculty of health sciences during the 2022-2023 academic year at a state university in the northeast region of Turkey. The sample size was determined using OpenEpi, version 3, statistical software with a confidence level of 95% and a power level of 80%, resulting in a minimum sample size of 168 students to represent the entire population. Being a 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th year student of the nursing department and volunteering to participate in the study were the inclusion criteria for the study. Using a simple random sampling, between March 15 and April 15, 2023, 260 nursing students with internet access and email addresses were included in the study.

2.4. Data collection tools

The data were collected using three instruments: the “Personal Information Form,” the “Conflict and Violence Awareness Scale (CVAS),” and the “Attitude Scale for Brain Drain (ASBD).”

The Personal Information Form: The form, created by the researchers based on literature (19-21), consists of 16 questions, with 9 questions related to the demographic characteristics of the nursing students and 7 questions aimed at assessing their thoughts about the nursing profession, health services, and the reasons behind brain drain.

The Conflict and Violence Awareness Scale (CVAS): To measure nursing students’ awareness of conflict and violence, the researchers utilized the Conflict and Violence Awareness Scale (CVAS), which was initially developed by the Ohio Department of Education and the Ohio Commission on Conflict Resolution and Conflict Management. (22). In 2010, Sargin obtained permission to translate this form into a scale and use it for scientific research. The CVAS is a 5-point Likert-type scale comprising 27 items applicable to both adolescents and adults. Respondents rate each item on a scale of “strongly disagree,” “disagree,” “partially agree,” “agree,” and “completely agree.” The total scores on the scale range from 27 to 135, with higher scores indicating a higher level of awareness of conflict and violence. The internal consistency coefficient of the scale was previously determined to be 0.87 (23). In this current study, Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient was calculated at 0.98.

The Attitude Scale for Brain Drain (ASBD): The scale developed by Öncü et al. (2018) to evaluate nursing students’ attitudes toward brain drain consists of a total of 16 items: 2 negative and 14 positive items. It has a one-dimensional and two-component structure (12 items are attractive factors, 4 items are repulsive factors). It is a 5-point Likert-type scale whose items are scored as “strongly disagree”, “disagree”, “undecided”, “agree” and “strongly agree”. The lowest and highest scores to be obtained from the whole scale are 18 and 80. Higher scores indicate a higher tendency toward brain drain. The Cronbach’s Alpha reliability of the scale is 0.91, and its subcomponents are 0.88 and 0.86 (15). In this study, the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of the scale was 0.93.

2.5. Data collection

The data were collected using a structured questionnaire created by the researchers in Google Forms and forwarded to the institutional e-mail addresses of the students through the student affairs unit. Çalışma gönüllülük esasına dayandırıldı. Participants provided their consent to participate in the study by completing a digital voluntary informed consent form. Once the consent was obtained, the questionnaire was activated, allowing participants to proceed with answering the questions. In the email, the purpose of the study, and the fact that no personal data would be collected and that the answers given would remain confidential were stated. The form takes approximately 10-15 minutes to complete. Link to the online questionnaire: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1HgaKZ9OCmmOqPTN4NHhHDE7TQnPm9tev7iAQzVKs2g/e/dit?pli=1>

2.6. Data evaluation

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 software. The normal distribution of the data was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation were utilized to analyze the data. In the analysis of the difference between independent variables, the Mann-Whitney U test was used for data with less than two groups that did not fit the normal distribution, and the Kruskal-Wallis test and Pearson correlation analysis were used for data with more than two groups. The data obtained were evaluated at a $p < 0.05$ significance level.

2.7. Ethical approval

Regarding the ethical aspects of the study, permissions and ethics committee approval were obtained before the study (Date: February 15, 2023, Decision No: 2023/053). To use the scales, written permission was sought from the authors who developed and validated the scales via email. Additionally, participants were provided with detailed information about the study on the online questionnaire's home page, emphasizing the protection of their personal information. The participation of students in the study was entirely voluntary. The research adhered to the principles of research and publication ethics throughout the study and publication processes.

3. RESULTS

The average age of the students was 21.12 ± 1.57 , and the average academic success was 2.72 ± 0.41 . 78.1% of the students were female, 53.8% resided in the city, 66.5% had an income equal to their expenses, 81.5% had a nuclear family family, 29.6% were in the 4th grade, and 50.4% had an intermediate level of foreign language (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Students (n=260)

	Mean±SD (Min.-Max.)	n (%)
Age	21.12±1.57 (18-27)	
Academic Achievement Average	2.72±0.41 (1.10-3.80)	
Gender		
Female		203 (78.1)
Male		57 (21.9)
Place of Residence		
City		140 (53.8)
District		97 (37.3)
Village/town		23 (8.8)
Income Level		
Income less than expenses		40 (15.4)
Income equal to expenses		173 (66.5)
Income more than expenses		47 (18.1)
Family Type		
Nuclear		212 (81.5)
Extended		48 (18.5)
Class		
1. grade		54 (20.8)
2. grade		63 (24.2)
3. grade		66 (25.4)
4. grade		77 (29.6)
Perceptions of Health Services in Turkey		
Good		15 (5.8)
Moderate		131 (50.4)
Low		95 (36.5)
Very low		19 (7.3)

Among the students surveyed, 60.4% stated that they chose the nursing department willingly, and 69.2% expressed their intention to pursue a career in nursing in the future. Concerning perceptions of the healthcare system in Turkey, 58.8% of the students assessed it at an acceptable level, and 44.2% regarded society's perspective on the nursing profession as acceptable. 74.2% of the students reported a desire for a better quality of life as their motivation. 75% highlighted the perception that qualified professionals are undervalued in their home country as a repulsive factor for seeking opportunities abroad. Notably, 34.6% expressed a post-graduation desire to work in a foreign country (Table 2).

Table 2. Students' Perspectives Regarding the Profession, Health Services, and the Causes of Brain Drain (n=260)

	n	%
Choosing the Nursing Profession Willingly		
Yes	157	60.4
No	25	9.6
Partly	78	30.0
Desire to Pursue the Nursing Profession in The Future		
Yes	180	69.2
No	19	7.3
Partly	61	23.5
Desire to Work Abroad After Graduation		
Yes	90	34.6
No	85	32.7
Partly	85	32.7
Society's Perception of The Nursing Profession		
Good	35	13.5
Acceptable	115	44.2
Poor	76	29.2
Very poor	34	13.1
Perceptions of Health Services in Turkey		
Good	63	24.2
Acceptable	153	58.8
Poor	31	11.9
Very poor	13	5.0
Attractive Reasons for Wishing to Work Abroad*		
The prospect of achieving a better quality of life	193	74.2
Seeking a higher salary	186	71.5
Foreign language education	169	65.0
More advanced research opportunities	156	60.0
Repulsive Reasons for Wishing to Work Abroad*		
Undervaluing qualified and skilled employees	195	75.0
Working conditions	194	74.6
Low salaries	192	73.8
Inequality of opportunity	191	73.5
The value attached to the profession	190	73.1
Problems in the education system	189	72.7
Failures in economic policies	182	70.0
Attitudes toward nursing/health workers (violence, insult, etc.)	179	68.8
Previous training that is undervalued in the workplace	177	68.1
Future anxiety	175	67.3
Not valuing science, art, and technology	174	66.9
Society's perspective on nursing	169	65.0
Politics affecting life	166	63.8
High unemployment rate	161	61.9
Lack of qualified managers	159	61.2
Frequent disasters such as floods and earthquakes in the country	143	55.0
*Multiple responses		

The mean total score was found to be 94.03 ± 25.32 for the CVAS and 54.27 ± 13.94 for the ASBD. The mean scores of ASBD were found to be statistically significantly higher in those who were male; in those who wished to work abroad post-graduation than those with a partial inclination or without it at all; and in those who evaluated the health services in Turkey and the society's view of nurses as "very poor" than those who evaluated them as "good, acceptable, and poor" ($p < 0.05$). The mean total score of the ASBD displayed no statistically significant variance concerning place of birth, income level, family type, or grade ($p > 0.05$).

No significant difference was found between the mean total scores of the CVAS and gender, place of birth, income level, family type, grade, desire to work abroad after graduation, thoughts about health services in Turkey, and society's perceptions of the nursing profession ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3. The Mean Total Scores of the CVAS and the ASBD According to Some Sociodemographic Characteristics and Students' Opinions about the Profession, Health Services, and Causes of Brain Drain (n=260)

	n (%)	ASBD		CVAS	
		Mean±SD	p ^{test}	Mean±SD	p ^{test}
The Mean Total Scores Of The Students in the CVAS and the ASBD					
		Mean±SD		Mean±SD	
		Min.-Max.		Min.-Max.	
		54.27±13.94		94.03±25.32	
		16-80		27-135	
Sociodemographic Characteristics					
Gender					
Female	203 (78.1)	52.8±13.5	0.002*	95.4±23.8	0.129***
Male	57 (21.9)	59.3±14.3		88.8±29.6	
Place of Birth					
City	140 (53.8)	54.0±14.3		93.7±25.8	
District	97 (37.3)	54.3±14.2	0.908**	96.4±24.2	0.146****
Village/town	23 (8.8)	55.2±9.5		86.1±25.7	
Income Level					
Income less than expenditures	40 (15.4)	58.3±13.4		94.1±26.8	
Income equal to expenditures	173 (66.5)	53.0±14.2	0.111**	94.0±25.0	0.820****
Income more than expenditures	47 (18.1)	55.2±12.8		93.8±25.7	
Family Type					
Nuclear	212 (81.5)	53.8±13.8	0.310*	94.9±25.1	0.323***
Extended	48 (18.5)	56.1±14.2		90.2±25.8	
Class					
1. grade	54 (20.8)	52.0±11.5	0.051**	99.3±20.2	
2. grade	63 (24.2)	51.4±13.7		91.5±24.2	0.281****
3. grade	66 (25.4)	54.0±14.5		89.3±31.7	
4. grade	77 (29.6)	58.3±14.4		96.3±22.6	
Desire to Pursue Nursing Profession in the Future					
Yes	34.6	64.0±12.0		90.5±29.6	0.257****
No	32.7	44.9±11.7	0.000**	95.0±22.5	
Partly	32.7	53.3±10.7		96.7±22.7	
Perceptions of Health Services in Turkey					
Good	24.2	49.6±14.7		95.7±24.7	
Acceptable	58.8	54.4±12.4	0.000**	93.4±24.3	0.821****
Poor	11.9	57.0±16.0		95.0±25.8	
Very poor	5.0	68.0±11.9		90.6±37.9	
Society's Perception of the Nursing Profession					

Good	13.5	49.2±14.3	0.031**	99.0±24.0	0.150****
Acceptable	44.2	54.2±12.7		90.6±25.3	
Poor	29.2	54.4±14.1		96.5±22.2	
Very poor	13.1	59.1±15.5		94.7±31.6	

*Independent t-test, **One Way ANOVA, ***Mann Whitney U, ****Kruskal Wallis H,

There is a significant negative correlation between CVAS and ASBD ($p < 0.05$). In addition, there is a significant positive correlation between age and ASBD ($p < 0.05$); and between age and academic achievement average ($p < 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4. The relationship between age, mean academic achievement, ASBD, and CVAS

	CVAS	ASBD	Age	Academic Achievement Average
CVAS	-			
ASBD	$r = -0.294$ $p = 0.000$	-		
Age	$r = -0.046$ $p = 0.465$	$r = 0.193$ $p = 0.002$	-	
Academic Achievement Average	$r = 0.040$ $p = 0.516$	$r = -0.085$ $p = 0.172$	$r = 0.276$ $p = 0.000$	-

Pearson Correlation Analysis

4. DISCUSSION

The detrimental consequences of violence targeting healthcare professionals, a growing concern within Turkey, also impact nursing students. As the demand for competent nursing personnel persists both nationally and globally, along with the anticipation that this need will continue in the forthcoming years, it becomes imperative to assess the perceptions of nursing students toward migration and the associated determinants of such migration. Considering this context, this section engages in a discussion on the outcomes derived from this research aimed at determining the correlation between nursing students' levels of awareness regarding conflict and violence and their attitudes toward brain drain. These outcomes are discussed within the framework of the relevant literature.

In accordance with the findings of the present study, the primary attractive reasons for seeking employment overseas encompass the prospect of a better quality of life abroad and the aspiration for a higher salary. Comparable motives were identified in a study carried out in the Philippines, which revealed that nursing students from the Philippines have intentions of international migration to strategize their education and career pursuits, improve their standard of living, and secure greater financial prospects (24). Likewise, in an examination into the rationales behind the international migration of healthcare professionals, factors including the pursuit of higher income, the ability to remit foreign currency to their home countries, the aspiration to operate within health systems with superior working conditions and advanced equipment, opportunities for career advancement and further education, improved quality of life, and the betterment of prospects for their families were identified as driving forces for migration (11). Remarkably, in the current study, a substantial 75% of the participants reported that their motivation for seeking overseas employment stemmed from the perception that the value of skilled and proficient labor remains undervalued within our nation. In the study conducted by Ozdemir & Ilhan (2021), participants identified the challenges encountered during their educational journey, coupled with dissatisfaction toward state policies (issues of nepotism, rights, transparency, justice, and meritocracy), as pivotal motives of the phenomenon known as brain drain (25). In a separate investigation carried out by Goštautaitė et al. (2018) with

physicians, nurses, and medical students, socio-demographic, social, financial, and institutional factors were identified as having associations with the inclination to migrate (26). Our study's results are consistent with conclusions drawn from both domestic and international literature.

In this study, it can be inferred that students exhibited a positive tendency toward brain migration, as evidenced by a mean total score of 54.27 ± 13.94 on the ASBD. Additionally, students' awareness of conflict and violence surpassed the average, as indicated by a mean total score of 94.03 ± 25.32 on the CVAS. An investigation with 617 nursing students, aimed at exploring the attitudes and inclinations of prospective nurses in Turkey regarding brain drain, highlighted an average total score of 53.88 ± 11.03 on the ASBD, signifying an elevated inclination toward migration and favorable attitudes toward the same (19). Conversely, another study by Demiray et al. involving 589 nursing students revealed a mean total score of 42.98 ± 9.91 on the ASBD, which fell below the average range (20). A study by Filiz et al. showed that medical faculty students exhibited a mean total score of 63.50 on the ASBD, indicating a marked inclination toward brain drain (21). In line with these findings, it can be said that among students studying in the field of health, positive brain drain attitudes are higher in students studying in medical faculties, followed by nursing students. An important finding of this study is that one third of the students (34.6%) reported that they wanted to work abroad after graduation. Based on the findings derived from the present investigation, more than half of the students (58.8%) offered an assessment categorizing the state of health services in Turkey as "acceptable." The students who found the Turkish health care system "very poor" had higher mean scores (68.0 ± 11.9) on the ASBD than those who found it "poor, acceptable, and good". Likewise, in a study by Filiz et al. involving medical faculty students, 46.1% of participants evaluated the efficacy of health services in Turkey as "acceptable." Notably, in that study, students who found the Turkish health system "very poor" had higher attitude scores toward brain drain than their peers who held more favorable opinions regarding the system's performance (21).

Within the scope of our study, most participants (44.2%) were inclined to categorize societal perceptions of the nursing profession as "acceptable." The mean total ASBD scores of the students who evaluated society's perceptions of nurses as "very poor" were significantly higher than the other groups ($p < 0.05$). A similar pattern was observed in the study conducted by Filiz et al. (2022), where 48.5% of students attributed a negative societal perspective to physicians; those students demonstrated an elevated tendency toward brain drain, contrasting with students who reported a more positive societal perspective; the latter group exhibited less inclination for migration (21). The findings of the study conducted with students in health-related departments are similar. The society's perspective on the profession and the attitude it develops and the attitude of the members of the profession are elements that feed each other.

A significant positive correlation was found between the ASBD and age ($p < 0.05$). This corroborates the results of Kizito et al. (2015), who, in their investigation of student physicians, also noted a notable connection between age and the inclination toward brain drain (10). Conversely, the study by Goštautaitė et al. (2018) on health professionals revealed a negative relationship between age and brain drain attitudes, signifying a decrease in brain drain tendencies as participants' ages advanced (26). Comparable conclusions were arrived at in another study, where a statistically significant variance between age and the ASBD mean total scores was identified ($p < 0.05$) (19).

According to our results, a significant negative correlation was found between the CVAS and the ASBD of nursing students ($r = -0.294$; $p < 0.05$). While the relevant literature contains studies that assess the awareness of conflict and violence among nurses and diverse cohorts, there remains a notable gap in the exploration of the connection between nursing students' level of awareness regarding conflict and violence and their attitudes toward brain drain. However, in a study conducted with nursing students, it was determined that the students' income status, foreign language proficiency and knowledge of the nursing profession abroad had an effect on the brain drain tendency (27). In this study, as nursing students' awareness levels toward conflict and violence increase, their tendency

toward brain drain decreases. This result is thought to be improved by preventing possible conflicts and negative perceptions between health workers and society and by reviewing the country's health policies, as the future graduates tend to remain in their countries and practice their professions.

Limitations of the study

The main limitation of this study is its restriction to nursing students from a single university department. Therefore, the outcomes cannot be generalized to all nursing students.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it is believed that this study, undertaken to explore the relationship between nursing students' awareness of conflict and violence and their inclination toward brain drain, yields valuable insights that can make significant contributions to the existing body of literature and may serve as a foundational reference for the design and execution of more comprehensive investigations. The study's outcomes underscore that the brain drain tendencies observed among nursing students surpass the average, and notably, these tendencies diminish with increased awareness of conflict and violence.

It is remarkable and unfortunate that the brain drain tendency of the students is above average. In recent times, there has been a growing perception that various factors, including labor strikes within the healthcare sector, inadequate wage prospects, increased cases of violence targeting healthcare professionals, and increased work demands due to the ongoing pandemic, have collectively contributed to an upward inclination toward "brain drain" among nursing students.

"NURSING STUDENTS' AWARENESS LEVEL OF CONFLICT AND VIOLENCE AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS BRAIN DRAIN: A DESCRIPTIVE AND RELATIONAL STUDY" Research and Ethics Statement
Information for the Article with Title

This study has been prepared in accordance with the values of 'Research and Publication Ethics' and has been checked by a plagiarism control programme. All responsibility for the study lies with the author(s).

Information	-
Author Conflict of Interest Statement	There is no conflict of interest among the authors.
Financial Support	No
Author Contribution Statement	The authors contributed equally to this article.
Thanks	-
Ethics Committee Approval Certificate	Ethics Committee approval has been obtained.
Scale Permit	Scale permission has been obtained.

REFERENCES

1. Yalçın, H. (2023). Violence and Rates of Violence Against Healthcare Professionals. *Aydın Journal of Health* 9(3): 117-130.
2. Budden, L.M., Birks, M., Cant, R., Bagley, T., Park, T. (2017). Australian Nursing Students' Experience of Bullying and/or Harassment During Clinical Placement. *Collegian* 24(2): 125-133.
3. Maffissoni, A.L., Sanes, M.D.S., Bresolin, P., Martini, J.G., Schneider, D.G., Lino, M.M. (2021). Self-reported Violence by Nursing Students in the Context of Undergraduate Studies. *Revista Brasileira de Enfermagem* 74(4): e20201179.
4. Cheung, K., Ching, S.S., Cheng, S.H.N., Ho, S.S.M. (2019). Prevalence and Impact of Clinical Violence Towards Nursing Students in Hong Kong: A Cross-Sectional Study. *BMJ Open* 9(5): e027385.

5. Newman, C., Roche, M., Elliott, D. (2021), Exposure to Workplace Trauma for Forensic Mental Health Nurses: A Scoping Review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies* 117:103897.
6. Park, J.E, Kim, D.H., Park, J.H. (2017). Violence Against Nursing Students During Clinical Practice: Experiences, Perception, Responses and Coping with Violence. *Journal of the Korea Academia-Industrial Cooperation Society* 18(10): 652-662.
7. Tee, S., Özçetin, Y.S.Ü., Russell-Westhead, M. (2016), Workplace Violence Experienced by Nursing Students: A UK Survey. *Nurse Education Today* 41: 30-35.
8. Scherer, Z.A.P, Scherer, E.A., Rossi, P.T., Vedana, K.G.G., Cavalin, L.A. (2015). Expressions of Violence in the University Environment: The View of Nursing Students. *Revista Eletrônica de Enfermagem* 17(1): 69-77.
9. Gokbayrak, S. (2008). The Debates on International Migration and Development: An Investigation on Brain Drain. *Ankara Faculty of Health Sciences Journal* 63: 65-82.
10. Kizito, S., Mukunya, D., Nakitende, J., Nambasa, S., Nampogo, A., Kalyesubula, R., Katamba, A., Sewankambo, N. (2015). Career Intentions of Final Year Medical Students in Uganda After Graduating: The Burden of Brain Drain. *BMC Med Educ* 15: 122.
11. Yıldırım, T. (2009). Health Workers and International Migration: A Study on the Causes of Migration. *Journal of Ankara University Faculty of Medicine* 62(3):87-94.
12. ILO. Promoting Decent Work Across Borders: A Project for Migrant Health Professionals and Skilled Workers. Published 2014. Available at. http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/@asia/@ro-bangkok/@ilomanila/documents/publication/wcms_214081.pdf. (accessed July 10, 2023).
13. Aluttis, C., Bishaw, T., Frank, M.W. (2014). The Workforce for Health in a Globalized Context--Global Shortages and International Migration. *Glob Health Action* 7: 23611.
14. World Health Organization. The World Health Report, 2006, Working Together for Health, Available at. http://www.who.int/whr/2006/whr06_en.pdf.
15. Öncü, E. (2018). Globalization and Changing Nursing Workforce within the Framework of Flexibility Model. *Journal of Human Sciences* 15(2): 1185-1192.
16. Turan, F.D. (2021). Career Decision and Career Decision-Making Competences as the Determinants of Nursing Fourth Grade Students' Attitudes Towards Brain Drain. *Gümüşhane University Journal of Health Sciences* 10(4): 828-841.
17. Bakırtaş, T., Kandemir, O. (2010). Developing Countries and Brain Drain: Example of Turkey. *Kastamonu Education Journal* 18: 961-974.
18. Kıran, B., Taşkıran, E.G. (2015). Overview of Nursing Education and Manpower Planning in Turkey. *Mersin University School of Medicine Lokman Hekim Journal of History of Medicine and Folk Medicine* 5(2): 62-68.
19. Seven, A., Adadoğlu, O. (2022). Nursing Students' Attitudes Towards Brain Drain in Turkey: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Türkiye Klinikleri J Nurs Sci* 14(1): 179-184.
20. Demiray, A., İlaslan, N., Acıl, A. (2020). Evaluation of Nursing Students 'Attitudes Towards Brain Drain. *Journal of Human Sciences* 17(2): 632-641.
21. Filiz, M., Karagöz, M.B., Karagöz, N. (2022). Evaluation of Attitudes of Medical Faculty Students Towards Brain Drain. *The Black Sea Journal of Social Sciences* 14(27): 679-692.
22. Ohio Department of Education and the Ohio Commission on Dispute Resolution and Conflict Management (2002). *School Conflict Management Resource Guide for Grades 7-12*. Ohio: State Board of Education.
23. Sargın, N. (2010). Examining Prospective Teachers' Conflict and Violence Awareness Levels by Some Variables. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice* 16(4): 601-616.
24. Ortiga, Y.Y. (2018). Learning to Fill the Labor Niche: Filipino Nursing Graduates and the Risk of the Migration Trap. *RSF: The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences* 4(1): 172-187.
25. Özdemir, A., İlhan, A. (2021). The Brain Drain: A Qualitative Study in the Context of the Reasons Leading Students into Education Abroad. *Istanbul Commerce University Journal of Science* 20(42): 1159-1186.
26. Goštautaitė, B., Bučiūnienė, I., Milašauskienė, Ž., Bareikis, K., Bertašiūtė, E., Mikėlionienė, G. (2018). Migration Intentions of Lithuanian Physicians, Nurses, Residents and Medical Students. *Health Policy* 122(10): 1126-1131.
27. Gençbaşı, D., Üzümcü, L.Y., Yavuz, D., Üstün, S.M., Türkoğlu, R.F., Bagheriyar, E., Yetkin, İ.E. (2024). Determination of Nursing Students' Attitudes Towards Brain Drain at a University and the Affecting Factors. *Journal of Health and Nursing Management*. 11(1): 180-187.